

Ring-Closure of *o*-Thiocarbamidobenzoic Acids : Studies in Isomerism.

BY TEJENDRA NATH GHOSH.

When anthranilic acid and phenyl mustard oil are allowed to react in the cold, *o*-phenylthiocarbamidobenzoic acid (I, R=Ph) and 4-keto-2-thio-3-phenyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroquinazoline (II, R=Ph) are obtained (McCoy, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 21, 147). Anthranilic acid has now been condensed with various mustard oils in hot alcoholic solution and in each case only the corresponding quinazoline has been obtained. This shows that the arylthiocarbamidobenzoic acid which is first formed very easily passes into the quinazoline with loss of a molecule of water.

(where R = phenyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-tolyl, 1:3:4-xylyl, and allyl).

A remarkable transformation takes place when compound (II, R=Ph or *p*-tolyl) is heated with strong sulphuric acid at 125-130°. The products of the reaction are isomeric with the original substances but possess different properties.

In fact, the compound (II) is acidic in nature and gives a disulphide, whereas its transformation product (III) is insoluble in alkali but soluble in acids. The alternative formula (IV) is rejected on the ground that the compound actually isolated is not desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury. As no intermediate product has been isolated, it is difficult to suggest, at present, the real mechanism of the above reaction.

The action of concentrated sulphuric acid upon *o*-phenylthiocarbamidobenzoic acid also leads to the compound (III, R=Ph).

The behaviour of 4-keto-2-thio-3-allyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroquinazoline appears to be different from that observed with the other quinazolines, in so far as it gets decomposed on boiling with strong sulphuric acid giving rise to a sulphur-free crystalline compound (m. p. 207°). The yield of this compound is so poor that further studies could not be made. When, however, the compound (II, R=allyl) is boiled with strong hydrochloric acid, 2-allylamino-6-keto-4:5-benzo-1:3-thiazine (III, R=allyl) is obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Keto-2-thio-3-phenyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroquinazoline (II, R=Ph).—An alcoholic solution of anthranilic acid (5 g.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath with phenyl mustard oil (5 g.) for about an hour when a crystalline precipitate was obtained, which crystallised from acetic acid in colourless plates, m. p. above 300° (yield 7 g.). (Found: N, 11.19. $C_{14}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 11.02 per cent.). It is soluble in cold dilute alkali, and insoluble in sodium carbonate or bicarbonate solutions. It gives an insoluble lead salt with lead acetate.

Disulphide.—Iodine solution (in potassium iodide) was added drop by drop to an acetic acid solution of the above compound (II) and gently warmed. On dilution with water it gave a yellowish amorphous mass which was washed free from excess of iodine with potassium iodide solution, water and finally with alcohol; m. p. 250-252°. (Found: N, 11.31. $C_{28}H_{18}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 11.06 per cent.).

4-Keto-2-thio-3-p-tolyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroquinazoline (II, R=p-tolyl).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound. It was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless plates, m. p. 310°. (Found: N, 10.42. $C_{15}H_{12}ON_2S$ requires N, 10.44 per cent.).

4-Keto-2-thio-3-o-tolyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroquinazoline (II, R=o-tolyl).—Obtained in a similar manner it crystallised from acetic acid in colourless plates, m. p. 268-270°. (Found: N, 10.04. $C_{15}H_{12}ON_2S$ requires N, 10.44 per cent.).

The *disulphide* was prepared in the usual manner; m. p. 215° (shrinking at 200°). (Found: N, 10.12. $C_{30}H_{22}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 10.48 per cent.).

RING-CLOSURE OF *o*-THIOCARBAMIDOBENZOIC ACIDS 983

4-Keto-2-thio-3-(1':3':4')-xylyl-1:2:3: 4-tetrahydroquinazoline (II, R=xylyl).—It was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless plates, m. p. 259-260°. (Found: N, 9.54. C₁₆H₁₄ON₂S requires N, 9.93 per cent.).

4-Keto-2-thio-3-allyl-1:2:3: 4-tetrahydroquinazoline.—It was crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 206-207°. (Found: N, 13.25. C₁₁H₁₀ON₂S requires N, 12.84 per cent.). It is soluble in dilute caustic soda and insoluble in sodium carbonate or bicarbonate solutions.

2-Anilino-3-keto-4: 5-benzo-1: 3-thiazine (III, R=Ph).—(a) 4-Keto-2-thio-3-phenyl-1:2:3: 4-tetrahydroquinazoline (5 g.) was heated with strong sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) in an oil-bath at 125-130° for 3-4 hours. The clear solution, thus obtained, was cooled and diluted with cold water when a precipitate came out which further crystallised from alcohol in fine colourless needles, m. p. 184-185°. (yield, 3.5 g.). It is insoluble in both cold and hot alkali. (Found: N, 11.27; S, 13.01. C₁₄H₁₀ON₂S requires N, 11.02; S, 12.59 per cent.).

(b) *o*-Phenylthiocarbamidobenzoic acid (4 g., prepared according to the method of McCoy, *loc. cit.*) was heated with strong sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) in an oil-bath at 125-130° for about 3 hours. The clear solution, on dilution with ice-cold water, gave a precipitate which crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 184-185°. (yield, 1.5 g.). It is insoluble in both cold and hot alkali. (Found: N, 11.31. C₁₄H₁₀ON₂S requires N, 11.02 per cent.). The identity of this compound with that prepared by the above method was further confirmed by determining a mixed melting point.

2-*p*-Tolylamino-6-keto-4: 5-benzo-1: 3-thiazine (III, R=*p*-tolyl).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound. It was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 235°. It is insoluble in cold or hot alkali. (Found: N, 10.48. C₁₅H₁₂ON₂S requires N, 10.44 per cent.).

2-Allylamino-6-keto-4: 5-benzo-1: 3-thiazine (III, R=allyl).—4-Keto-2-thio-3-allyl-1:2:3: 4-tetrahydroquinazoline (5 g.) was boiled with hydrochloric acid (50 c.c., *d* 1.19) for about 3 hours. The clear solution was allowed to cool when shining colourless needles came out which crystallised from hot water; m. p. 231-232°. It is the hydrochloride of a base and soluble in warm water from which the free base was obtained by the addition of dilute caustic potash solution. The base crystallised from hot water in shining colourless needles; m. p. 115° (yield, 3 g.) It is insoluble in cold

water and in cold dilute alkali. (Found: N, 13.15; S, 14.25. $C_{11}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 12.84; S, 14.67 per cent.).

Further work in this line is in progress.

My best thanks are due to Professor P. C. Guha, D.Sc., for the kind interest he has taken in this investigation.

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received June 27, 1930.